

Corporate Governance Theories: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to check, does agency and stewardship theories are complimentary to each other which will help the researchers to understand the similarity and difference in beliefs and understandings of both the theories. These theories are applied in different environments and circumstances based on the location where company is operating and the governance structure of the corporate. The relationship between principle and agent plays important role to increase efficiency and productivity of the organisation. Both principle and agent has its own goals but when it differs there are chances of conflict in the organisation. Agency theory supports the separate role of the CEO and chairman of the board, because when CEOs are powerful the interest of the shareholders are jeopardise. Stakeholder theory facilitates the idea of CEO and Chairman of the board being a one. Both stewardship and agency theory cannot be applied together because of difference in their basic understandings

Key words: agency theory, stewardship theory, CEO duality, independent directors.

INTRODUCTION

Corporate governance is a process through which corporates are managed and controlled. Good corporate governance contributes to the corporation's economic sustainability by improving the performance, value and enhancing their access to outside capital (**Shao, 2017**) Corporations are republics. The number of components of a corporate governance structure is shareholders; board of directors, characteristics of board, board committee management and interaction of these corporate agents examine and explore the firm performance and value. There are three aspects of the decision-making process in the firm in which corporate governance is concerned. First, who is authorised to take what kind of decisions; Second who gets priority while taking a particular decision; Third why and how social, political, economic and legal associations impacting the decision making process.

There are certain theories which define the proper explanation and applicability of the corporate governance in particular organisation. We have selected two controversial theories for this study.

Agency theory is a most popular theory among all the existing theories on corporate governance and it has received the enormous attention from researchers, academics and practitioners (**Jensen and Mackling, 1976**). The main focus of the agency theory is to save the interest of the shareholders unlikely stakeholder theory (**Fama and Jensen, 1983**). Stewardship theory is a complimentary theory to the agent theory but it is sophisticated and speaks more about behavioural aspects (**Fast et al, 2012**).

The important function of board of the directors is to protect the interest of the stockholders and importantly define the relationship between CEO and the chairman of the board (**Tricker, 1984**). The appointment of chief executive as a chairman and appointment of independent directors has become huge conflict between agency and steward theory (**Donaldson and Davis, 1991**). These two theories have different understanding and judgement on the CEOs appointment (**Kreiser et al., 2010**). The shareholders interest is not safe when chairman of the board is a CEO of the organisation unless the interests of the chief executive and shareholders are not common (**Williamson, 1985**). The different beliefs on appointment of independent directors are also a matter of debate while agency theory is against the appointing independent directors and also believes that their interference in management will cause the agent problem in the organisation (**Bhagat and Black, 2002**). The result of governance theories is hard to generalise because different countries follow different corporate governance policies and practices based on their own political and cultural values (**Yusoff and Alhaji, 2012**).

Review of literature

AGENCY THEORY

The concept of agency theory was first introduced by some economists in late 1960 for the purpose of risk sharing problems among the individuals or groups. The agency problem arises when different parties or individuals have different attitudes, goals and vision (**Ross, 1973**). The agency problem describes the relationship in which one party handover its work to another party to work on their behalf. The agency theory is all about solving the two major problems which already exist between two parties. The one problem is when there is difference in desired goals and vision between principles and agents. The second problem is when there is difference in perceiving risk attitude between principle and agent as they may prefer separate actions as per their preferences (**Jensen and Mackling, 1976**). The conflict between principle and agent leads the separation of owners and management in the organisation. In organisation shareholders are principles and managers are agents working in the interest and on behalf of principles. Agency theory attempts to build proper function for effective control for corporates to make managers

and directors to act in the best interest of stakeholders (**Allen and Gale, 2001**). When the control of the firm is separated from its owners, managers or agents may or may not act always in the best interest of the shareholders. (**Baysinger and Hoskisson, 1990**) claimed that managers are satisfying themselves rather than maximising the value of the firm for its shareholders. If the incentives like stock options, perquisites and bonuses are given and proper monitoring like agents bonding, managements perquisites systematic review, and financial audit is done principles can make themselves sure those agents will make optimal decisions for their firm and the agents will not make appropriate decisions until the governance structure is not made in the organisations (**Jensen and Mackling, 1976**). The interest of the shareholders will not be saved until the board is held by CEOs unless they have a same interest as a shareholder does (**Williamson, 1985**).

The agency theory is not all about existence of conflict between principles and agents it also talks about generation of wealth for the shareholders by allocating the funds good projects and generating the outside capital for the organisation and many more issues related to the business (**Lafontaine, 1992**).. The large number of studies had been done till the time across the universe on corporate governance and its impact and role with companies performance by taking agency theory as a mediator. The agency theory also talks about separation of the role of CEO and members of the board will give better results (**Donaldson and Davis, 1991**). The dependence of agency theory or problem is on the ownership characteristics of the companies of each country. Countries in which ownership structure is not concentrated or the control of the company is in the hands of large number of shareholders, if there is any disagreement or disappointment between management and investor regarding company performance or any other issue they have option to exist (**Spanos, 2005**).

Figure 1. The Agency Model
Adapted from Abdallah, H. (2009)

STEWARDSHIP THEORY

The theoretical basis of stewardship theory is based on psychology and sociology concentrates on the behaviour of managers. Stewardship theory is a contrary of agency theory where it explains the managers are the good stewards and works for the best interest of the principles/shareholders (**Donaldson & Davis 1991**). The researchers argue that the motivational alternative for the managers in is the stewardship theory in which the executive managers will be doing a good job and be a good steward for the companies' assets rather than searching for opportunistic shirker (**Donaldson, 1990; Barney, 1990**). The behaviour of the steward is always a pro-organisational and the steward's main concern to achieve organisational objectives collectively (**Davis, Schoorman & Donaldson 1997; Qiao, et al, 2017**). There is a strong relationship between organisational with the maximization of shareholders wealth, the stewards benefits are maximized too in which stewards are having clear mission (**Smallman, 2004**). Stewardship theory builds a understanding and trust between the owner/principle and manager which leads the organisation towards innovation (**Zhang, et al, 2017**). Stewardship theory defines the relationship between the organisational success and managers by maximising and protecting the wealth of the shareholders through organisational performance i.e satisfying and serving the interest of the stakeholders in the organisation which leads to increase the wealth of the organisation. When the single person holds the power of CEO and the chairman the responsibility to take important decisions and determine the strategies for the organisations remains in one hands. The focus of the stewardship theory is not upon to CEOs motivation it is mainly upon the structure which facilitates and empowers the organisation rather than controlling and managing it (**Davis, et al, 1997**). The stewardship theory supports facilitates the idea of appointing the one person for the CEO and chairman job, and more executives directors rather than non-executives directors (**Clarke, 2004**). The theory of stewardship is relevant to define the role of internal audit in the organisation because this theory is all about the collective or common interest of the principle and manager (**Zhang, Wei, Yang & Zhu, 2017**). The motivation of the managers in the non-profit organisation in the light of relevance the stewardship theory as compared to the agency theory which explains that the factors behind the motivation of employees is because of coordination, understanding and friendly environment in the organisation (**Kluvers & Tippett, 2011**). The oneness in the spirituality, financial decision making and stewardship is essentially important for the organisations survival and the failure of the organisations and economies can be traced with the absence of spirituality and stewardship (**McCuddy & Pirie, 2007**).

Figure 3. The Stewardship theory
Adapted from Abdallah, H. (2009)

METHODOLOGY

In this study we used a systematic review by collecting the literature review related to the field of study. This study used journal articles which are having highest citations. From top 200 cited articles from different sources such as Google scholar, emerald insight, Elsevier and science direct. The 50 articles were selected by using random function in MS Excel.

This study aims to contribute in the area of corporate governance by conducting the systematic approach. We have attempted to study the two most popular theories of corporate governance, agency theory and stewardship theory. The reason of selecting these two theories is because these theories are complimentary to each other. As corporate governance is an area in which a number of researchers had contributed since 1976 and still researchers has no common understanding on it. Further this study will be helpful for the future researchers to contribute on.

AGENCY THEORY VS STEWARDSHIP THEORY

DIMENSIONS	AGENCY THEORY	STEWARDSHIP THEORY
MEANING	Agency theory is economic model which describes the relationship between principle and agent	It is a human model which describes the relationship between principle and steward
Relationship	Shareholder/principle & agent	Shareholder/principle & steward
Relationship basis	Control	Trust
Model	Management & economic	Psychology & sociology
Motivation	Extrinsic	Intrinsic
Approach	Control	Collaboration
Organisational identification	Low level	High level
Human behaviour	Individualistic/opportunistic/self-serving	Collectivistic/pro-organisational/trustworthy
Governance mechanism	Monitoring and incentives	Empowering structure
Owners attitude	Risk avoidance	Risk taker

AGENCY THEORY VS STEWARDSHIP THEORY

The coexistence of agency and stewardship theory has complimentary view for each other, but the applicability of both depends upon the attitude of the shareholder/principle and manager/agent respectively. (Yusoff and Alhaji, 2012) also argue that the applicability of existing governance theories also depends upon the environment where the corporations are operating because the corporate governance policies and practices may differ from nation to nation due to the social, political, historical and cultural settings.

The agency and stewardship theory have their different perspectives and conceptions, but the ultimate motive of the both theories is that agent or manager will be working on behalf of the principle/shareholders to maximise the value of the firm. Agency theory upholds that both principle and agent will work wisely and sensibly to increase their utilities, which will eventually lead to the minimization of expenditures and maximization of their personal income (Jensen and Mackling, 1976). It is obvious that the both principle and agent will have their own motives and purposes, but if it differs then the possibilities of conflict will arise. Stewardship theory comes to an existence as a compliment to agent theory with a more humanistic and not entirely limited economic and value maximization concept.

Agency theory entails that there are two proper corporate governance structures that prevent the conflict between managers and shareholders, one is appointment of the independent directors and second is separation of board chair from management. Agency theory did not support the idea of dual role in the organisation it argues that if CEO is also a chairman of the board then they may act to benefit themselves rather than the shareholders (**Jensen and Mackling, 1976**). While as stewardship theory supports and facilitates the idea of CEO being a chairman of the board. Stewardship theory stressed upon that when CEO is a member of the board and getting a proper incentives then he will view himself a steward and will for the welfare of the corporation by minimizing the costs, and conflicts (**Donaldson and Davis, 1991**). Being a CEO and chairman of board as a one CEO will feel more powerful and efficient that will help him to improve the productivity, efficiency and also he will properly manage the assets of the firm to generate better returns (**Cornforth, 2004**). (**Fast et al, 2012**) point out that when CEO has power he become overconfident then he might work in a way to increase his own compensation which will have harmful impact on corporates long term performance. But if the interest of the CEO and shareholders are common, powerful CEO will not left any stone unturned to improve the performance of the firm (**Daily and Johnson, 1997**). The empirical studies on performance of the firms shows mixed response, some studies showed that CEO being a chairman of the board has negative impact or no impact at all on share returns (**Boyd, 1995; Duru et al, 2016; Elsayed, 2007**). while as in the support of stewardship theory researchers found that there is a significant positive impact on firm performance and also the communication efficiency is strong between the management and the board (**Rashid, 2010; Gill and Mathur, 2011; Guillet, 2013**).

Agency theory suggests that appointing independent directors and their no influence in management will prevent the agent problem in the organisation, there are different arguments on this suggestion neither there is any conclusive evidence that independent directors have positive impact (**Bhagat and Black, 2002**) and nor there is any argument which leads us to conclusion that there is no need of independent directors. In this contrast stewardship theory suggests that it is unnecessary to have outside directors in the board, because the stewards are the believers of collectivism and motivated to work for the best interest of the principles (**Luan & Tang, 2007**). Stewardship theory further outlined that stewards are the responsible and inherently trustworthy, and not inclined to misappropriate the resources of the organisation (**Barney, 1990**).

CONCLUSION

The accountable members of the board make sure that the interest of the stockholders is not in risk. The trust of the investors and shareholders will gain when there is an accountability and transparency in policies and practices of corporate governance. The implication of agency and stewardship theory has their own consequences agency theory is more about the saving the interest of shareholders limited to the economic and value maximization prospective. while as stewardship has similar concept to serve the shareholders but it's more complex and in humanistic manner, and also introduced in a behavioural prospective. The outcome of existing theories of corporate governance will not reach to its conclusion because of difference in policies and practices across countries due to social, political, historical, and cultural environment. The CEO duality has become major argument between the researchers and practitioners collectively which has made these two theories more complex and conflicting while at first stewardship theory was introduced as a compliment to the agent theory.

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